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Improved visualisation of ACP-engineered osteoblastic spheroids: a comparative study of contrast-enhanced micro-CT and traditional imaging techniques

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Abstract

This study investigates osteoblastic cell spheroid cultivation methods, exploring flat-bottom, U-bottom, and rotary flask techniques with and without amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP) supplementation to replicate the 3D bone tissue microenvironment. ACP particles derived from eggshell waste exhibit enhanced osteogenic activity in 3D models. However, representative imaging of intricate 3D tissue-engineered constructs poses challenges in conventional imaging techniques due to notable scattering and absorption effects in light microscopy, and hence limited penetration depth. We investigated contrast-enhanced micro-CT as a methodological approach for comprehensive morphological 3D-analysis of the *in-vitro* model and compared the technique with confocal laser scanning microscopy, scanning electron microscopy and classical histology. Phosphotungstic acid and iodine-based contrast agents were employed for micro-CT imaging in laboratory and synchrotron micro-CT imaging. Results revealed spheroid shape variations and structural integrity influenced by cultivation methods and ACP particles. The study underscores the advantage of 3D spheroid models over traditional 2D cultures in mimicking bone tissue architecture and cellular interactions, emphasising the growing demand for novel imaging techniques to visualise 3D tissue-engineered models. Contrast-enhanced micro-CT emerges as a promising non-invasive imaging method for tissue-engineered constructs containing ACP particles, offering insights into sample morphology, enabling virtual histology before further analysis.

1. Introduction

The field of bone tissue engineering (TE) is the focal point of extensive research aimed at developing materials capable of replicating the specific mechanical stiffness and strength essential for bone's functional integrity [1]. This necessity underscores bone's dynamic nature—a tissue that undergoes continuous adaptation and remodelling in response to mechanical loadings [2, 3]. Such dynamics necessitate TE

strategies that align with the specific needs and states of the target bone [4].

Central to the success of these strategies is the design and selection of scaffolds or templates, which critically influence cellular behaviour and the remodelling of the bone matrix [5–8]. Collagen, a fundamental organic constituent of bone, embodies this principle. Its function as a dense scaffold for osteoblast deposition and remodelling, as well as a site for mineralisation, has been utilised in models

demonstrating the potential for rapid development of woven or immature bone within 21 d [9, 10]. While traditional collagenous materials have been extensively studied, amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP), distinct from the more explored crystalline calcium phosphate (CaP) materials, has captured significant interest due to its diverse physicochemical properties, excellent bioactivity and remarkable biodegradability [9, 11, 12]. Forming from supersaturated calcium-phosphorus solutions, ACP serves as a crucial precursor to CaP's mineral phase and acts as a reservoir for calcium and phosphorus, which plays a pivotal role in regulating bone tissue formation and mechanical properties [13–15]. In previous work, we synthesised ACP particles from eggshell waste rich in trace elements (Mg and Sr). We established a cell interaction spheroid model based on a differential precipitation strategy, which could replicate the spatial microarchitecture of natural bone more accurately and facilitated ACP to exhibit higher osteogenic activity than in the 2D model [16]. However, this work only focused on the osteogenic behaviours of cells under a single-gravity loading mode. Therefore, clarifying the interaction between cells and ACP particles under various mechanical environments is crucial to understanding and developing more realistic *in-vitro* 3D-research models for bone graft materials.

As the complexity of these models increases, classical light microscopy methods become limited for in-depth analysis due to scattering and absorption by induced minerals or early ossification, restricting the analysis to the surface.

This analytical restriction in the advancements in bone TE underscores a commitment to developing novel methodologies, including virtual histology derived from micro-CT, that offer deeper insights into the intricate interactions between engineered materials and bone tissue bypassing the limitations from classical imaging techniques, paving the way for the regeneration of healthy bone.

Micro-CT (μ CT) provides unparalleled resolution and three-dimensional visualisation of bone structures, enabling researchers to examine the microarchitecture of bone spheroids during osteogenesis [17]. This allows for the detailed observation of bone formation, mineralisation patterns, and the distribution of biomaterials within the spheroids without the need for decalcification for imaging, thus being minimally perturbative.

However, incorporating contrast-enhanced μ CT into the analysis of bone spheroids represents a significant advancement in bone TE research, allowing the visualisation of non-mineralised components, as already demonstrated for soft tissue spheroids [18], along engineered materials and bone tissue. This section elucidates why contrast-enhanced μ CT is

pivotal in studying osteoblastic spheroids and the broader field of bone regeneration.

The 3D reconstructions offered by μ CT facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the spatial relationships and interactions within the bone matrix, which are critical for assessing the efficacy of TE strategies.

One of the most significant advantages of contrast-enhanced μ CT is its non-invasive nature, which allows samples to be preserved for further analysis [19]. This is particularly important in longitudinal studies, where the progression of bone development or the behaviour of biomaterials over time needs to be monitored. Researchers can perform sequential imaging at various stages of the experiment without compromising the integrity of the spheroids, thereby gaining dynamic insights into the processes of bone regeneration and material degradation.

μ CT provides qualitative insights and enables precise quantitative analysis of bone tissue and engineered scaffolds. Parameters such as bone volume fraction, porosity, and trabecular thickness can be accurately measured [20], offering objective data to assess and compare the performance of different biomaterials and TE approaches. This quantitative capability is essential for validating the effectiveness of bone regeneration strategies and guiding scaffold design optimisation.

The application of contrast agents in μ CT significantly enhances the differentiation of soft tissues within the spheroids, which is often challenging to achieve with conventional imaging techniques along bone or opaque biomaterials. This improved contrast is crucial for studying the interface between engineered materials and the surrounding bone tissue and visualising the vascularisation and soft tissue integration vital for bone regeneration.

Using contrast-enhanced μ CT aligns with the evolving needs of bone TE research, providing a sophisticated tool to study the complex biological processes involved in bone regeneration. By offering detailed visualisation, quantitative data, and the ability to perform subsequent analysis, contrast-enhanced μ CT propels the field forward. It enables researchers to dissect the mechanisms of action of biomaterials, assess their performance in a physiologically relevant context, and refine TE strategies to address clinical challenges in bone repair and regeneration.

Here, we aim to compare classical visualisation methods—confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and classical histology—of ACP particle-containing bone spheroids without prior decalcification with contrast-enhanced μ CT. Further we demonstrate the influence of cultivation methods and the utilisation of ACP particles on osteoblastic spheroids using contrast-enhanced μ CT. Iodine- and phosphotungstic acid

(PTA)-based contrast agents were employed with both synchrotron micro-CT and laboratory micro-CT imaging. Results were compared with CLSM, SEM, and classical histology.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Particles and spheroid cultivation

The previously described dissolution-precipitation method synthesised the 'control' ACP [21]. First, 10 g of HAp powder (#04238; Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was added to 600 ml of deionised water (dH₂O) that was magnetically stirred at 200 rpm. After 10 min, 3 M HCl solution (64.46 ml) was added to the obtained HAp suspension, resulting in the dissolution of HAp. 10 min after the acid was added, the stirring rate of the solution was increased to 600 rpm, and 2 M NaOH aqueous solution (91.5 ml) was rapidly poured into it. The pH of the synthesis media increased to ~11.0 and led to the formation of a white precipitate. After 5 min, the stirring was discontinued, and the precipitate was filtered and washed on a filter paper with dH₂O. Then, the precipitate was transferred to plastic containers immersed in liquid nitrogen. Freeze drying was used to remove the excess water from the frozen precipitate. To synthesise the 'Eggshell' ACP, eggshells (provided by eggs and egg-product producer 'Balticovo' (Lecava, Latvia) were firstly thermally treated at 900 °C for 1 h to decompose the organic matter and transformed CaCO₃ to CaO. Then 5.55 g of the obtained CaO was added to 600 ml of dH₂O that was magnetically stirred at 200 rpm. The addition of CaO resulted in the formation of a white suspension. After 10 min, 12.47 ml of 4.76 M H₃PO₄ solution was added to the suspension. The rest of the synthesis steps, starting from the HCl solution addition step, are the same as described in the 'control' ACP synthesis. 2) To avoid unwanted biological and chemical contamination, ACP particles were cleaned and sterilised before the biological experiments. In brief, ACP particles were resuspended in dH₂O (0.1 g/5 ml), centrifuged at 2400 rpm for 2 min, and the supernatant was discarded entirely. Afterward, ACP particles were resuspended again in 75% ethanol for 30 min by applying an orbital shaker. After spinning down, the particles were rewashed with absolute ethanol, filtered with 0.22 µm sterile syringe filter (CLS431224, Corning, USA), and dried on a heater (45 °C) for 30 min [16].

MC-3T3-E1 osteoblastic cells (CRL-2593, ATCC, USA) were cultured in α -MEM medium with 15% fetal calf serum (FCS, 20170-106, Gibco, USA) and Penicillin (P, 100 units ml⁻¹)/Streptomycin (S, 100 µg ml⁻¹) at 37 °C with humidified 5% CO₂. Cells were passaged at 80% confluency.

For 3D spheroids establishment, cells were resuspended, and their density of 1 × 10⁶ cells ml⁻¹ was adjusted. To build the Control cell spheroids, 200 µl cell resuspension per well was seeded into a

U-bottom non-adherent 96 well plate (BIOFLOAT™ 96 well plate, faCellitate, Germany) and cultured for 24 h to obtain osteoblastic spheroids. To build ACP-embedded spheroids, 200 µl cell resuspension per well was seeded in the same BIOFLOAT 96 well plate and cultured for 0.5 h to allow the preliminary sedimentation of the single cell layer, followed by adding ACP particles (100 µg/well) and culturing step for additional 23.5 h to form ACP-embedded osteoblastic spheroids. Then, three groups of spheroids were cultured in α -MEM medium with 15% FCS and 50 µg ml⁻¹ ascorbic acid (A5960, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) under different environments for 7 d: (1) in a 24-well plate (flat surface, 12 spheroids/well), (2) in a 96-well U-bottom plate (U-bottom surface, 1 spheroid/well), and (3) in 10 ml CelVivo ClinoReactor at rotating speed of 25.0 rpm (Rotary flask, 10004-1, CelVivo, USA).

2.2. Contrast enhancement and preparation for micro-CT

A multiparametric study design was utilised for a comprehensive understanding of the technique used: spheroids were examined in two different modalities, three cultivation techniques, and different preparation methods.

2.2.1. Preparation for cone beam micro-CT (CBµCT)

Samples from flat-bottom and U-bottom well plate cultivations were scraped from the well plate and isolated. The specimens were incubated in 0.3% PTA in water for 24 h each, rinsed in water and then placed inside a sealed 200 µl pipette tip (Mettler-Toledo Rainin, Oakland, CA, USA) in water for scanning in CBµCT.

2.2.2. Preparation for synchrotron radiation micro-CT (SRµCT)

Samples from rotary flask cultivation were dehydrated in 70%, 80%, 90% and 100% ethanol for 15 min each and divided into three subgroups for individual contrast enhancement: (i) control, (ii) 0.3% PTA in ethanol for one day, and (iii) 1.0% I₂E also for one day. The residual contrast agent was removed by replacing the solution with 100% ethanol after 15, 30 and 45 min and subsequently xylene by replacing the agent after 20, 20 and 45 min. Final wax incubation was performed utilising paraffin (Eprexia, Kalamazoo, MI, USA) type 1 for 30 min, type 6 for 30 min and type 9 for 30 min at 60 °C before terminal embedding in sealed 200-µL pipette tips (Mettler-Toledo Rainin, Oakland, CA, USA) for scanning in SRµCT. All micro-CT scanned samples are summarized in table 1.

2.3. Cone beam micro-CT (CBµCT)

Samples from flat-bottom and U-bottom well plate cultivations were scanned by a nano-CT (SkyScan 2211 Multiscale x-ray Nano-CT System, Bruker

Table 1. Overview of spheroid samples for μ CT imaging.

Cultivation method	Sample type	Imaging method	Contrast agent	Number of samples
Flat-bottom	Control	CB μ CT	0.3% PTA	1
	Control-ACP	CB μ CT	0.3% PTA	1
	Eggshell-ACP	CB μ CT	0.3% PTA	1
U-bottom	Control	CB μ CT	0.3% PTA	1
	Control-ACP	CB μ CT	0.3% PTA	1
	Eggshell-ACP	CB μ CT	0.3% PTA	1
Rotary	Control	SR μ CT	No stain, 1.0% I ₂ E, 0.3% PTA	5, 5, 4
	Control-ACP	SR μ CT	No stain, 1.0% I ₂ E, 0.3% PTA	5, 5, 5
	Eggshell-ACP	SR μ CT	No stain, 1.0% I ₂ E, 0.3% PTA	4, 5, 5

micro-CT, Kontich, Belgium) with a 20–190 kV tungsten x-ray source and 11-megapixel cooled $4,032 \times 2670$ pixel CCD-camera. The specimens were scanned at 40 kV, 300 μ A and 1200 ms exposure time over 360° with a rotation step of 0.23° , leading to a final voxel size of 0.5 μ m. The scan duration for samples was about 1.5 h. Micro-CT projections were reconstructed using the system-provided software NRecon (version 1.7.4.6) with ring artefact correction 12 and beam hardening correction of 50 %. The images were visualised and analysed with Dragonfly (Comet Technologies, Montréal, Canada, version 2022.2).

2.4. Synchrotron radiation micro-CT (SR μ CT)

Samples from rotary flask cultivation were scanned at the Synchrotron Radiation for Medical Physics (SYRMEP) beamline in the synchrotron laboratory ELETTRA (Trieste, Italy) using a sample-to-detector distance of 100 mm and a 0.5 mm silicon filter. The projections were obtained with 16.7 keV and 308 mA, an exposure time of 50 ms over 180° , and 1800 projections. The pixel size was set to 0.9 μ m. Reconstructions were performed using STP (version 1.6.2), a custom reconstruction program of SYRMEP. Analysis was performed in Dragonfly 3D World (Comet Technologies Canada Inc, Montréal, Canada, version 2024.1, Build 1601) and (mean) Feret diameter, volumes and aspect ratios were measured from 3D-based region of interest resulting from segmentation of the spheroid. The Feret diameter, also known as the caliper diameter, refers to the distance between two parallel lines (or planes in 3D) that just touch opposite sides of a particle. In 2D, this is the distance between two tangents to the particle's outline. Since the value depends on the particle's orientation, a single measurement is not very meaningful. So, several measurements are taken in different angles. The ratio between the maximum and minimum Feret diameter is known as aspect ratio [22, 23].

2.5. Confocal microscopy

The ACP treatment and grouping were the same as described in 2.1. In brief, spheroids were cultured for 7 d in the CelVivo flask with speed of 25 rpm and

then fixed with 4 wt.% PFA for 20 min. After washing in PBS thrice, samples were treated with 0.1% (v/v) TritonX-100 (X100, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) for 20 min, followed by blocking in 1 wt.% BSA/PBS solution for 1 h. Then, the samples were incubated in goat-anti-mouse osteopontin (OPN) primary antibody (Ab) (AF808, R&D systems, USA) at 4°C overnight. After incubation, samples were washed in PBS for 5 min on a shaker thrice and subjected to the incubation of Alexa Fluor™ 488-labelled Chicken anti-Goat secondary Ab (1:1000, A21467, Invitrogen, USA) for 1 h at room temperature. The cell nuclei were counter-stained with DRAQ5 (62251, Thermo Scientific, USA). After washing with PBS, samples were mounted and observed by laser scanning confocal microscope (SP8, Leica, Germany). 3D images were captured with stacks and reconstructed by Fiji software (NIH, USA).

2.6. Histology

Samples from rotary cultivation were fixed in 4% PFA supplemented with 1% glutaraldehyde, dehydrated with 70%, 90% and 100% ethanol for 15 min each, followed by replacing the 100% ethanol after 15, 30 and 45 min. The clearing was performed with xylene with replacing the agent after 20, 20 and 45 min. Wax incubation was performed using paraffin type 1 for 30 min, type 6 for 30 min and type 9 for 30 min at 60°C before final paraffin embedding in standard moulds. Sections of 5 μ m were obtained with Leica RM2255 rotary microtome (Leica Biosystems Nussloch GmbH, Nussloch, Germany) and placed on glass slides. Subsequently, haematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was applied.

2.7. Scanning electron microscope/energy dispersive x-ray spectrometry (SEM-EDXS)

For SEM/EDXS analysis, samples from the rotary cultivation method were fixed in 4% PFA supplemented with 1% glutaraldehyde, dehydrated in a sequence of ethanol from 30% to 100% in 10% steps for 15 min, followed by immersion in hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS) twice for 15 min with subsequent air drying overnight on an aluminium stub on double-sided carbon tape. Samples were examined with Hitachi Analytical TableTop Microscope/Benchtop

SEM TM3030 in conjunction with EDS equipment (Bruker Nano GmbH, Berlin, Germany). An acceleration voltage of 15 kV was used with a working distance of 9800 μm and magnifications from 200 \times to 1,000 \times for imaging and EDXS. Acquisition times for EDXS measurements totalled 3 min.

3. Results

3.1. Cultivation-induced morphological alternations of spheroids

CB μCT of flat- and U-shape bottom, and SR μCT of rotary cultivated osteoblastic cell spheroids showed alternating shapes of the control spheroids, only containing cells (figure 1). While flat-bottom cultivation resulted in flat spheroids, U-shape cultivation resulted in spherical shapes. Spheroids cultivated in the rotating flask resulted in a spherical shape, without the characteristic opening in the bottom of U-shape cultivated osteoblastic cell spheroids, visible in the lateral view.

The addition of Control- and Eggshell-ACP induced three-dimensional shaping of the osteoblastic cell spheroids in flat-bottom cultivation, highlighted in the lateral cross-section in figure 2. However, the characteristic spheroid opening is still induced using the cultivation method, resulting in a hemispheric morphology. This is not observable in superior cross-sections. Added particles were not revealed in the expected amount in flat-bottom cultivation, but in rotary cultivation method.

3.2. Analysis of contrast-enhanced osteoblastic spheroids from rotary flask cultivation

Osteoblastic cell spheroids, cultivated in a rotary flask, containing no synthetic and eggshell-derived ACP particles were contrast-enhanced using 1% iodine or 0.3% PTA or were scanned with the SR μCT in the propagation-based phase-contrast imaging. Simultaneously, spheroids were analysed with confocal microscopy (figure 3(a)). While contrast-enhanced μCT was able to image the spheroid throughout the entire sample, confocal microscopy revealed the first micrometres from the upper hemisphere (figures 3(b) and (c)). Micro-CT images were artificially coloured in black to yellow, indicating increasing attenuation. Individual cells are recognisable, and Control-ACP and Eggshell-ACP are distributed throughout the sample. Cell-spheroids without the particles show homogeneously distributed cells and a sharp-defined border encapsulating the spheroid. Spheroids, which contain particles, show an irregular border with protruding ACP.

The ACP-containing particles' mean Feret diameter and volume are significantly higher than cell-spheroids (figure 4). Control- and Eggshell-ACP did

not show a significant difference. While the minimal, mean and maximal Feret diameter of cell-spheroids are similar, these parameters show differences in the ACP-spiked spheroids. Aspect ratios are accordingly lower with these spheroids, indicating an impaired sphericity. The comparison of the two different contrast agents with the obtained morphological parameters of the spheroids only imaged with phase-contrast revealed no clear effect of the dimensional analysis of the spheroids. However, the mean Feret diameter of Control-ACP spheroids was slightly reduced with PTA contrast enhancement (figure 4(e)).

Conventional histology from rotary flask cultivation, using H&E staining, showed the distribution of the cells in the cell-spheroids. Additionally, the observed encapsulating layer could be confirmed (figure 5, left top). ACP-spiked particles were distorted during mechanical slicing from paraffin embedding. However, particles could be confirmed along the cells. Furthermore, SEM-EDXS analysis showed the alternating morphology of the surface (figure 5, right): the entire spheroid without ACP showed elongated cells encapsulating the spheroid, while ACP-spiked spheroids showed an irregular surface with protruding ACP, detected by EDXS measurements as calcium and phosphorus in the indicated ratios. Further mapping of calcium, phosphorous and carbon and quantities of detected elements can be found in the supplements (figure A1).

4. Discussion

4.1. Why do we need bone spheroid models in bone engineering (or reconstruction)?

In Europe, around one-third of hospitalisations involve bone-related injuries or disorders, imposing significant healthcare costs. Age, gender, lifestyle, and genetics significantly influence bone healing and contribute to conditions like osteoarthritis and osteoporosis [24]. The prevalence of bone fractures, especially in the elderly due to osteoporosis, is increasing, with projections indicating a rise in hip fractures from 1.6 million to 6.3 million by 2050 [25]. This surge in bone-related issues has escalated the demand for bone implants and reconstructive materials; there is a pressing need for advanced orthopaedic research and improved treatment modalities [26]. Despite their widespread use in bone TE research, animal models often provide operational and batch-to-batch instability and face ethical and economic challenges [27, 28], as well as high bio-dost and potential environmental pollution [29–31]. EU and US regulatory efforts to reduce animal testing further support the shift from an *in-vivo* study to an *in-vitro* model. The EU Directive 86/609/EEC and its successor, Directive 2010/63/EU, emphasise the 3 R principles (Replacement, Reduction, and

Refinement) to enhance animal welfare in research [32]. These directives mandate prior approval for animal research, focusing on minimising animal use and suffering. In the US, recent legislation has moved towards making animal testing non-mandatory for FDA drug approvals, highlighting a global trend towards adopting alternative research methods. These developments underscore the growing importance of *in-vitro* models in orthopaedic research, offering a more ethical, economic, and potentially more effective approach to understanding and treating bone disorders [33–35]. While alternative spheroid and organoid models offer promising avenues to address ethical and economic concerns in biomedical research, they may only partially replace animal models. These advanced *in-vitro* systems provide a more controlled environment to study human-specific cellular behaviours and drug responses, thus reducing the reliance on animal testing. However, animal models still play a crucial role in capturing the complex interactions within an entire living organism, which is challenging to replicate entirely with spheroids and organoids. Rather than focusing on replacement, these *in-vitro* models serve as a bridge between traditional cell cultures and animal models. They help refine the early stages of research, offering insights that can better inform subsequent animal studies.

The goal is to try to replace or reduce the use of animal models where possible. Still, integrating both methods ensures a more comprehensive understanding of biological processes and disease mechanisms. By complementing each other, spheroids, organoids, and animal models push the boundaries of research, ultimately enhancing the accuracy and applicability of scientific findings.

4.2. Advantage/dis growing bone cells flat, U-shape and rotatory condition

Due to its unique mechanical properties and structural composition, the complexity of replicating the human bone physiological environment calls for *in-vitro* models that can offer more accurate and ethical alternatives for studying bone diseases and evaluating new therapies [36]. However, conventional *in-vitro* models for investigating the biofunctions of bone graft materials are mainly based on 2D culture, which neither reflects the hierarchical structure of natural bone tissue nor provides spatial interaction between materials and osteoblastic lineage cells [37, 38]. In addition, lacking organic and inorganic extracellular matrix, such a 2D cell culture model was proven to have a limited application prospect in bone reconstructive and graft materials research [39]. In contrast, 3D models utilising cells offer a more

faithful reproduction of bony architecture by providing the necessary environment for cellular organisation and microvasculature development around mineralised deposits [40]. Due to the spatial features close to the *in-vivo* milieu during osteogenesis and

organogenesis, 3D models provide cells a platform to perform unique biofunctions [38]. Tumour cells in spheroids form were also reported to have a significantly higher drug resistance against chemotherapy than in 2D culture [41, 42]. However, due to

uneven mineral distribution, these models often fail to replicate the bone's detailed nanoscale features, observed weeks after seeding. Alternative methods such as scaffolds, 3D-printed bone organoids, microfluidic devices, and bioreactors have been developed to address these shortcomings. These approaches facilitate efficient cell aggregation, promote tissue maturation and functionality, and emulate the mechanical properties of bone more accurately than simpler models. They offer the advantages of simpler manipulation and precise monitoring of biochemical and biomechanical stimuli, closely mirroring the true complexity of bone tissue and its mineralised matrix. Such models not only support high-throughput studies and flexible modification of experimental conditions but also enhance the detection of cellular reactions [43, 44]. Primarily used for exploring bone formation and investigating related diseases, these bone models also play a crucial role in evaluating new treatments [45].

According to the novel 3D organoids culture strategy concept, a low-cost 3D osteoblast spheroid culture system was established in our previous study using a readily available U-shaped well-plate with a non-adhesive surface [16]. Exploiting the differential sediment dynamics of cells and ACP materials, osteoblasts could wrap ACP particles (figure 5) and induce more active osteogenic behaviours in such osteoblastic spheroids than that in 2D culture system. However, our previous study only performed a subsequent culture on a 2D plane after the construction of cell spheroids. Due to the monotonous force-bearing method, the osteoblastic spheroids still showed differences compared to the real osteogenic microenvironment *in-vivo*. Moreover, the relatively large size (>500 microns) and opacity make it impossible to detect the internal structures of the cell spheroids with a confocal microscope, let alone the detailed interactions between osteoblasts and ACP particles [16]. Based on high-resolution micro-CT

and contrast-enhancement approaches, a new solution was established in this study to investigate the internal structures of cell spheroids. Through this non-invasive method, we were able to observe the structure inside the cell spheroids while preserving

the integrity of the sample, and for the first time, provided direct evidence based on 3D reconstruction to prove that single-directional gravity force modes caused the collapse and reshaping of the cell spheroids. At the same time, a rotary circumstance

could maintain the structural stability and original cell distribution of spheroids (figure 1). 3D virtual slicing confirmed that ACP particles support the spatial structure of spheroids and attenuate and structural collapse of spheroids under a single-gravity environment (figure 2). It is worth noting that fluid shear stress (FSS) exerted on spheroids in a rotary environment may further enhance their osteogenic functions, which can partially simulate the functions of FSS (triggered by blood flow and physical activity) in natural bone tissue [46]. Incorporated ACP particles change the surface and sphericity (figures 3(b) and 4) and thus influence FSS and spheroid development, explaining the elongated cells in the spheroid surface in the control spheroids.

4.3. Why add ACP particles to bone cells? What are the advantages? Why ACP and no other bioceramics?

CaPs are essential for bone regeneration, functioning through several mechanisms. They initiate osteogenesis by releasing ions that attract bone-forming cells and encourage the deposition of carbonated apatite, a process that also captures growth factors essential for bone formation [47, 48]. CaPs serve dual roles in bone healing: osteoconduction, which facilitates the transformation of progenitor cells into bone-forming cells, and osteoinduction, which involves attracting cells to the regeneration site [49, 50]. For *in-vitro* bone spheroid models, incorporating CaP ceramics and scaffolds enriched with osteoprogenitor cells is crucial to accurately mimic the natural process of bone matrix development and functional regulation by osteocytes [51]. Research has shown various CaP materials to be influential in bone formation. *In-vivo* models have demonstrated that ACP, as an initial phase, plays a pivotal role in apatite growth, facilitating subsequent bone development facilitated by alkaline conditions within mitochondria [41]. Compared with other bioceramics, CaPs materials provide naturally metabolisable calcium and phosphorus components for bone formation with a physiological ratio [42, 52], which forms the mineralised cores and maintains the osteogenic tendency of the local milieu. The application of CaPs avoids introducing other structural elements (such as Si in Bioactive glass-ceramics and Si-substituted hydroxyapatite (HAp). Etc.), making the microenvironment free from interference from other ions [52]. For these reasons, adding CaPs to cell cultures for growing bone spheroids is necessary. It provides a biomimetic environment that closely replicates the natural bone's ionic composition and mineral phases. It promotes osteoprogenitor cells' differentiation and maturation into bone cells [53, 54], accurately modelling bone tissue's complex structure and functionality. Furthermore, including CaPs in

cell cultures enhances the mechanical stability of the spheroids, providing the necessary scaffolding for cell attachment and growth [50]. It also facilitates studying bone formation and disease pathology under conditions that closely mimic the *in-vivo* environment, allowing for more accurate assessment of therapeutic interventions. Despite the well-documented ability of HAp to promote bone formation [55, 56], its high crystallinity and stoichiometric properties limit its solubility compared to natural bone apatite, which can reduce its effectiveness [57]. In contrast, ACP exhibits variable physicochemical properties, excellent bioactivity, and enhanced biodegradability, making it a compelling alternative [58, 59]. ACP initially forms a solid phase from a supersaturated calcium-phosphorus solution, with a Ca/P ratio close to 1.5, serving as a precursor to the mineral phase of CaP [59, 60]. This characteristic allows ACP to modulate the rate of bone formation and improve mechanical properties by adjusting the Ca/P ratio in the surrounding tissue [61]. *In-vivo* studies, such as [specific *in-vivo* studies], indicate that ACP can be deposited by intracellular vesicles at collagen matrix fibril gaps, acting as a precursor for bone apatite growth in developing bone [58, 59, 62–64]. Furthermore, ACP supports osteoblastic cell growth and differentiation, with ACP micron-fibre sponges demonstrating excellent osteoconductive properties and facilitating the maturation of human alveolar bone [13].

4.4. Why use ACP from Eggshell and not just synthetic ACP?

CaPs derived from eggshells over synthetic counterparts in bone spheroid cultures present a multifaceted argument that hinges on sustainability, biological compatibility, and economic efficiency [65, 66]. Eggshell-derived CaPs, a byproduct of food consumption, offer an eco-friendly alternative to synthetic CaPs, aligning with the principles of green chemistry and waste valorisation [16]. This approach also leverages a readily available resource, potentially lowering the cost of CaP procurement for bone regeneration research [67]. Eggshell-derived CaPs exhibit a unique microstructural resemblance to the mineral component of human bone, potentially enhancing the bioactivity and osteoconduction in bone spheroid cultures. The organic matrix of eggshells, rich in proteins and other bioactive molecules, may contribute to the osteoinductive properties of the derived CaP, facilitating the recruitment and differentiation of osteoprogenitor cells [68]. This organic-inorganic interplay is less pronounced in synthetic CaPs, often produced through chemical processes that need a more nuanced composition of natural bone [69]. From a practical standpoint, the extraction process of CaPs from eggshells can be less energy-intensive than

the synthesis of CaPs, offering an additional environmental and economic benefit. Moreover, the variability in the physicochemical properties of eggshell-derived CaPs can be tailored through controlled processing, allowing for the customisation of the material to suit specific research needs. Besides the crystalline CaP materials, the variable physiochemical properties, excellent bioactivity, and superior biodegradation of ACP make it an attractive bone graft material. As the 'pool' of Ca and P, ACP acts as the precursor of the mineral phase of crystalline CaPs and regulates bone formation and mineralisation by adjusting Ca/P content in natural bone tissue [61]. ACP can dissolve in an aqueous environment rapidly and release Ca^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} , followed by the recrystallisation and growth of HAp [70]. This may explain the increased Ca/P ratios of 2.07 ± 0.13 for eggshell-ACP and 2.32 ± 0.13 for control-ACP found in spheroids in EDXS measurements (figure 5). *In-vivo* and *in-vitro* evidence confirmed that ACP can deposit at the collagen fibrils' gap zones and initiate bone HAp-like structure formation, thereby supporting rapid bone formation and maturation [13, 71–73]. Compared with HAp, ACP exhibited a similar excellent osteoconduction but higher osteogenic activities, manifested by the elevated proliferation, alkaline phosphatase synthesis and OPN expression in MC-3T3-E1 cells [13, 74]. Even though they are both ACP, Eggshell ACP has higher osteogenesis-beneficial magnesium and strontium content than synthesised ACP from pure HAp [16]. Notably, Eggshell-ACP could promote the OPN deposition on the particles and form a tight bond between cells and materials, which forms a structural basis for supporting the spatial structure of spheroids (figure 5) [16]. Furthermore, using eggshell-derived ACP in bone spheroid cultures underscores the commitment to minimising utilising sustainable materials in scientific research, reflecting a growing trend towards minimising laboratory practices' carbon footprint. By repurposing waste into valuable biomedical resources, researchers can contribute to a circular economy, demonstrating the feasibility of integrating sustainable practices into biomaterials research.

4.5. How to evaluate these bone spheroids and compare different strategies?

Contrast-enhanced micro-CT has substantially improved contrast for soft tissues, e.g., cartilage [59, 60], and various other biological samples such as insects, amphibians, fish, mouse and chick embryos [75–79]. Additionally, it has been valuable in assessing the ultrastructure of the human cornea in our prior research [80]. Nevertheless, sample preparation has to be evaluated and is reported to change samples properties, such as volume due to the low pH of PTA

solution and the high osmolality of Lugol's iodine [81]. Furthermore, concentration-dependent effects regarding sample shrinkage of I_2KI contrast enhancement have been documented [82].

Our investigation measured spheroids with both PTA- and iodine-based contrast enhancement alongside unstained samples using phase-contrast imaging from synchrotron radiation. This approach enabled an evaluation of the contrast agent's influence on the general morphology of spheroids, revealing no discernible trends in diameter or volume change across the samples (figure 4). However, it is essential to acknowledge that previous sample preparation, including dehydration and wax embedding, likely contributed to shrinkage. This effect can be anticipated to be consistent across all groups, differing solely in the employed contrast agent. Wax embedding for synchrotron-based imaging techniques was chosen to avoid generating bubbles during image acquisition, producing artefacts and loss in image quality. For laboratory micro-CT imaging, 0.3% PTA in water yielded optimal results, allowing visualisation of individual cells within the entire spheroid, comparable to the level of detail achieved in an optimised contrast-enhancing protocol for native human corneal tissue [80]. These results underscore the broad utility of contrast-enhanced micro-CT in imaging both native tissues and tissue-engineered products. Moreover, the image quality of laboratory micro-CT was sufficient to observe individual cells and its distribution and revealed the overall shape of the spheroid, offering the potential to bypass the dehydration and embedding process of the sample for scanning in synchrotron facilities and thus reduce methodological bias of sample preparation.

Contrast-enhanced micro-CT enables analysis of samples exceeding the maximal penetration depth achievable with laser confocal microscopy, which is reported to be a few hundred micrometres [83]. In our study, we investigated spheroids with CLSM and micro-CT. While CLSM provided analysis of the spheroids' upper hemisphere, micro-CT allowed visualising the morphology of the entire spheroid that showed mean diameters of $429 \pm 86 \mu\text{m}$ for cell spheroids to $982 \pm 63 \mu\text{m}$ for eggshell-ACP-spiked spheroids. However, despite the comprehensive visualisation capabilities of micro-CT, specificity and the range of the available staining agents for confocal microscopy and the resolution cannot be achieved by contrast-enhanced micro-CT yet. Further analysis with advanced 3D optical imaging approaches, like multi-photon or multi-view light sheet microscopy, are likely to surpass the observations achieved in confocal microscopy. However, these methods also require optically clear tissues to achieve optimal imaging results

[84]. Truong *et al* has demonstrated high imaging depths using a combination of two-photon laser point-scanning microscopy and selective-plane illumination microscopy, the two-photon scanned light-sheet microscopy (LSM) of entire fly embryos [85]. Spatial sampling of 400 voxels \times 900 voxels \times 200 voxels (x , y and z , respectively) with voxel sizes of 0.635 μm \times 0.635 μm \times 1 μm with additional z -stacking were applied to archive the 3D imaging. Due to the sample size of about 1 mm in diameter and approximately 50% of ACP particles which induce a notable heterogeneity and enormous density, we anticipate that the entire volume cannot be visualised by the advanced techniques either. For this reason, contrast-enhanced micro-CT enabled a unique technology to visualise the entire spheroid, including its particles and the cells, which allows for analysis of particle and cell distribution achieved by the different cultivation approaches. Table 2 summarizes the differences of CLSM imaging against SR μ CT and CB μ CT, and theoretically multiphoton microscopy (MPM) and LSM, for visualising the bone spheroid samples from this study.

Further, conventional histology was performed on the spheroid samples. It was observed that paraffin embedding is unsuitable for sectioning spheroids containing ACP particles, as illustrated in figure 5. While alternative embedding methods, such as resin embedding, may improve the section quality, the possibility of distortion cannot be entirely eliminated [89]. Conversely, contrast-enhanced micro-CT does not require dehydration for embedding, thereby limiting potential changes in ultrastructure or overall morphology to the fixation and contrast-enhancement agent. However, like CLSM, the specificity of commercially available staining kits for conventional histology and resolution of microscopes remains beyond the capabilities of laboratory contrast-enhanced micro-CT. Nevertheless, contrast-enhanced micro-CT facilitates virtual histology, opening the possibility for virtual sectioning post-scan and virtual re-orientation considering the morphological characteristics of the sample (figures 1 and 2). This approach may reduce bias introduced by the orientation achieved during the embedding process before sectioning and enables the reuse of samples for subsequent analyses following scanning.

To our knowledge, the detailed imaging of spheroids has yet to be previously demonstrated. A recent investigation explored the morphology of spheroids derived from malignant (WM266-4) and primary (WM115) cell lines using contrast-enhanced micro-CT with Lugol's iodine and PTA [18]. However, the concentration of PTA amounted to 10% and iodine to 0.35 %, different from our protocols using 0.3% PTA and 0.5%–1% of iodine and hence significantly lower concentrations for PTA. Opposed to the findings of

Karimi *et al*, employing smaller voxel sizes in conjunction with 0.3% PTA revealed finer details of spheroids within the specimen. This facilitated the examination of overall morphology (figure 4) and enabled qualitative assessment of individual cell morphology in cross-sections (figures 1 and 2).

5. Conclusions

The necessity for bone spheroid models in bone engineering and reconstruction is underscored by the escalating prevalence of bone-related injuries and disorders in Europe, coupled with the increasing demand for advanced orthopaedic research and treatment modalities. Traditional animal models face ethical, economic, and regulatory challenges, prompting a shift towards *in-vitro* models supported by EU and US regulatory efforts to minimise animal testing. 3D spheroid models offer a more accurate representation of bone tissue architecture compared to conventional 2D models, facilitating the study of bone diseases and evaluation of therapies.

Using CaPs, particularly ACP, in bone spheroid cultures provides a biomimetic environment conducive to osteogenic differentiation and bone formation. CaPs derived from eggshells offer sustainability, biological compatibility, and cost-effectiveness advantages over synthetic counterparts, aligning with principles of green chemistry and waste valorisation. Furthermore, ACP from eggshells exhibits superior osteogenic potential and mineralisation compared to synthetic ACP, making it an attractive option for bone TE. However, imaging complex 3D models, mainly containing ACP particles, is difficult and often limited.

Contrast-enhanced micro-CT allowed the assessment of osteoblastic cell spheroids, including ACP particles, and the comparison of different TE strategies, offering comprehensive visualisation capabilities and virtual histology. While conventional histology presents challenges with sectioning spheroids containing ACP particles, CLSM is limited in penetration depth. Contrast-enhanced micro-CT provided a non-invasive alternative with the potential for virtual sectioning and orientation adjustments post-scan, but also provides spatial scans of larger volumes compared to laser confocal microscopy.

In conclusion, the utilisation of 3D bone spheroid models, especially those integrating ACP sourced from eggshells, represents a promising approach for advancing the field of bone TE and reconstruction. Additionally, contrast-enhanced micro-CT, as a methodological approach, exhibits distinct advantages and limitations compared to conventional imaging methods. Despite its limitations in resolution and specificity of staining, it remains a promising tool for evaluating 3D cultures in TE. It offers the ability to analyse samples using subsequent complementary analysis methods.

Table 2. Comparison of confocal microscopy and SR μ CT and CB μ CT for bone spheroid imaging.

Parameter	Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM)	Synchrotron radiation micro-CT (SR μ CT)	Conventional bench-top micro-CT (CB μ CT)	Multiphoton microscopy (MPM)	Light-sheet microscopy (LSM)
Pros	High spatial resolution Suitable for live-cell imaging	High spatial resolution Phase contrast imaging allows soft tissue imaging (no contrast agents needed)	Accessible/widely available and cost-effective Low preparation effort	2–3 times deep tissue penetration than CLSM [86] Suitable for live-cell imaging; reduced phototoxicity	Fast acquisition times Large field of view
Cons	Limited penetration depth Ideally optical clear samples	Limited accessibility High costs Risk of bubble generation	Contrast enhancement necessary for low density materials Long image acquisition times	Ideally optical clear samples for high penetration depth [87] lower resolution than CLSM	Limited resolution Ideally optical clear samples
Spatial resolution	~200 nm (XZ-plane); ~500 nm (Y-plane)	Sub-micron to 1 μ m	~1–10 μ m	Up to ~230 nm (XZ-plane); ~930 nm (Y-plane) [88]	~1–6 μ m (depending on the setup and field of view)
Image acquisition time	~Several minutes; depending on the resolution and setting (pin hole, diffusion and line scan between or line by line.etc)	1.5 min	1.5 h	~Minutes to hours (depending on tissue sample and set up)	~Seconds to minutes (depending on sample size and set up)
Sample preparation time	~24 h: 15 min fixation, 20 min tritonX100 penetration + 1 h blocking, overnight primary antibody incubation, 1 h secondary antibody incubation	~24 h contrast enhancement Dehydration and paraffin embedding and mounting for scanning ~12 h	~24 h contrast enhancement	~24 h/similar to CLSM (depending on labelling); with decalcification and clearing longer	~24 h/similar to CLSM (depending on labelling); with decalcification and clearing longer
Rationale	High-resolution imaging for thin or transparent samples Imaging specific markers	Ideal for high throughput and excellent contrast	Suitable for routine imaging and low preparation efforts	Ideal for imaging higher thicknesses (ideally cleared); decreased sensitivity to scattering	Best for rapid imaging of large, cleared specimens

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Torben Hildebrand: Investigation, Formal Analysis, Writing—Original Draft, Visualization. **Qianli Ma:** Conceptualization, Writing—Review & Editing, Visualization. **Dagnija Loca:** Writing—Review & Editing, Resources. **Kristaps Rubenis:** Writing—Review & Editing. **Janis Locs:** Writing—Review & Editing, Resources. **Liebert Parreiras Nogueira:** Methodology, Writing—Review & Editing, Supervision. **Håvard Jostein Haugen:** Conceptualization, Writing—Review & Editing, Resources, Supervision.

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